

It ain't what you do – it's the way that you do it.

Steven Thomson

Senior Agricultural Economist and Policy Advisor
Scotland's Rural College

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Recent weeks have seen the publication of two reports that provide suggestions for pathways for Scottish agriculture to deliver on climate and biodiversity priorities. The Farming for 1.5 Degrees panel's final report "From here to 2045" and "The Transition to Future (Conditional) Agricultural Support" by NFUS offer the Scottish Government complementary thoughts from the industry on how policy can deliver on food production, climate change and biodiversity. The Farming for 1.5 report is a culmination of two years of evidence gathering whilst the NFUS policy briefing pulls together the work of the five Farmer Led Groups and suggests a way forward that the industry could buy-into.

I happen to have had a hand in both reports, and I have to say that the last two years have been a steep learning curve for me – particularly on climate change. Through the evidence taken by the Farming for 1.5 Degrees panel, and then looking at mitigation pathways for the Scottish Government I grew to understand that the scale of the task ahead of the industry over the next 10–20 years cannot be underestimated. Both these reports acknowledge this – and therefore both urge the Scottish Government to start the process of transition as soon as they conceivably can. As the 1.5 report puts it: "Doing the same thing next year as we did last year is no longer an option for farmers in Scotland."

Both reports acknowledge that there must be a transition period to future policy schemes, and that those future schemes should reward those who deliver on 'public goods'. Everyone agrees that the policy mix will undoubtedly get more complex as the industry and Government try and grapple with the most complex of challenges. That is why both reports call for early baselining – getting a better handle on the starting position through carbon audits, soil carbon analysis, etc. Once farmers know where they stand, then those needing to make improvements can be supported through grants and advice (as the NFUS proposal calls Transformative Support). Importantly, payment will ultimately be for delivering public goods – for which some farmers may need to improve (and be helped to improve) their performance but some may not but should still be rewarded for already delivering.

The Scottish Government are committed to greater conditionality on half of Direct Support by 2024, and both reports call for rapid increase in 'conditionality' that can deliver. Unlike the much maligned 'Greening' rules any new conditionality menu needs to deliver more for the climate and biodiversity and needs to include all land (including rough grazing areas). Further, enhanced conditionality should include coupled support schemes for beef and sheep (and dare I say it, LFASS). Any new conditionality must have flexibility to reflect different farming systems and geographies – as Farming for 1.5 call it – "a farmer's mitigation menu." The NFUS policy briefing explains how this can be achieved through the existing mechanisms – giving the industry and Scottish Government time to reflect on and evolve a new agricultural policy that is fit for purpose from 2025 onwards.

The industry has many of the tools in the bag to deliver already. More efficient use of fertilisers and manures, increasing legumes in rotations, nutrient budgeting, yield mapping, improved livestock health, fertility and growth, reduced or zero tillage systems, integrated pest management, farm woodlands, hedgerows, peatland and wetland restoration, renewable energy, electric vehicles, reduced fuel use, etc. can all play their part. Finding the right mix in the right place will be part of the challenge and therefore a new form of advice is likely needed. Further, the toolbox is ever expanding – agri-tech solutions are already looking promising on feed additives and selective breeding to reduce methane emissions from ruminants, and even more tools are in the pipeline.

Farming for 1.5 call for farmers and crofters to be given a choice of approaches: ‘precision’ or ‘nature value’ – to ensure all sectors and farm types can contribute through a low carbon pathway. The NFUS policy proposals also argues that active farmers in the future should be supported based on (a) how technical efficient they are (efficiency reduces GHG emissions per hectare / head), and (b) their biodiversity provisioning. In this NFUS model farmers would still receive direct income support – both area-based and coupled support – but there would be tiers of payments depending on what farmers are delivering to therefore incentivise delivery of outcomes. If the payment rates are set right, then those on the bottom tier should be stimulated to restructure or adapt practices to start delivering. Farming for 1.5 take it a step further – suggesting that from 2024 emissions reduction contracts should be introduced across all farm types underpinned by a management plan that fits their system and its future development, with a limited number of management interventions (akin to a sustainable development plan). The NFUS briefing is explicit that setting criteria for payment tiers needs serious considerations and recommended that officials establish a series of working groups to consider this alongside other important issues such as: defining activity; LFA support; smallholders; advice and innovation; tenants; new entrants; communications.

It is that last point, communications, that I believe is essential. As I have said before – if you know where you are going, at least you can start making plans of how you are going to get there. I think that the industry know that change is inevitable – and if you need convincing just look south to England’s rapid policy evolution, or the ongoing panic across the EU farming sectors as the impacts of the latest CAP reform announcements sink in. Ultimately Defra and the EU are trying to deliver on climate and biodiversity objectives – something both the NFUS and Farming for 1.5 Degrees approaches offer. I remain convinced that these industry approaches can deliver for Scotland, while retaining an element of income support and a focus on food production. As people start to think about what the future may mean for their system remember this is about delivering more public goods for public monies – and (as the song goes) “It ain’t what you do, it’s the way that you do it, And that’s what gets results!”